

In silico engineering of nuclear-targeted peptides targeting the AP-1 transcriptional complex

Zahraa Amer Al-Juboori¹

¹ College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Palestine Street, Baghdad, Iraq

² Department of Veterinary Public Health, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

Corresponding author: Zahraa Amer Al-Juboori (Zahraa_ammer@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq)

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Abstract

Activator protein-1 (AP-1) is a transcription factor implicated in tumor progression but remains difficult to inhibit pharmacologically due to its extended protein–DNA interface. Structure-guided docking of a curated peptide library against the AP-1 complex (PDB: 1FOS) prioritized the soybean-derived decapeptide SKWQHQQDSC as the top-ranked candidate in the docking workflow (GlideScore –9.396 kcal/mol), outperforming the reference peptide under identical conditions. Interaction analysis suggested dual engagement of AP-1 protein residues and DNA bases within the bZIP interface. A 200 ns molecular dynamics simulation of the peptide–protein complex (DNA excluded for focused interfacial analysis) supported structural convergence, preserved α -helical architecture, and persistent electrostatic contacts over the simulated timescale. Nuclear-targeted variants incorporating a classical NLS were evaluated using fully flexible docking. Progressive rigidification via α -helical EAAAK linkers improved structural convergence and minimized nonspecific NLS participation, with the double rigid-linker construct exhibiting the most focused binding mode. Overall, these findings support linker rigidity as an important design parameter in multifunctional peptide engineering targeting transcription factor interfaces.

Keywords

computational peptide design, molecular dynamics, nuclear localization signal, protein–DNA interface, structure–function analysis

Introduction

Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), accounting for approximately 85% of lung cancer cases worldwide, is frequently driven by aberrant receptor tyrosine kinase signaling, particularly via epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) activation. Targeted inhibition of EGFR has significantly improved clinical outcomes in selected patient populations; however, therapeutic resistance, secondary mutations, and compensatory downstream signaling

frequently limit durable responses (Kadhim et al. 2025). These limitations highlight the need to target deeper transcriptional regulators that integrate oncogenic signaling cascades. Activator protein-1 (AP-1) is a dimeric transcription factor that binds to the consensus DNA sequence 5'-TGAGTCA-3' and regulates gene programs controlling proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, inflammation, and stress responses (Angel and Karin 1991; Shaulian and Karin 2002). It orchestrates gene programs by translating external signals into transcriptional outcomes that

critically determine cellular fate, governing proliferation, invasion, and survival, positioning it as a critical transcriptional node in NSCLC progression (Adisheshaiah et al. 2007; Papavassiliou et al. 2023; Song et al. 2023).

Aberrant AP-1 activation is strongly implicated in tumorigenesis. Persistent signaling promotes uncontrolled cell-cycle progression, resistance to apoptosis, invasion, and metastasis. Elevated expression of AP-1 subunits has been documented across multiple malignancies, positioning AP-1 as a central transcriptional regulator within oncogenic signaling networks (Eferl and Wagner 2003; Ozanne et al. 2007).

Despite its biological importance, direct pharmacological inhibition of AP-1 remains challenging. As a transcription factor, AP-1 lacks deep, well-defined binding pockets suitable for conventional small-molecule inhibitors and has therefore been historically classified as “undruggable” (Darnell 2002; Lambert et al. 2018). Alternative approaches targeting protein–protein and protein–DNA interfaces have consequently gained increasing attention.

Peptide-based inhibitors provide a rational strategy for modulating transcription factor complexes. Compared to small molecules, peptides can engage extended and relatively shallow interaction surfaces with improved specificity and adaptable binding geometry. Advances in computational modeling and peptide docking have enhanced the feasibility of designing peptide modulators against intracellular targets, including transcription factors (Craik et al. 2013; Yin 2019).

Previous computational work has demonstrated that short peptides can interact with the AP-1 transcriptional complex and disrupt its functional interface (Kumar et al. 2021). However, effective inhibition of AP-1 requires not only target binding but also efficient nuclear localization. Incorporation of nuclear localization signals (NLSs) enables importin-mediated nuclear transport but introduces additional design complexity, including increased length and charge density that may interfere with binding specificity if not structurally controlled (Cronshaw et al. 2002; Lange et al. 2007).

The aim of this study was to establish a structure-guided computational framework for engineering nuclear-targeted peptide inhibitors of the AP-1 transcriptional complex, with particular emphasis on defining how linker architecture governs functional domain segregation and binding specificity. Specifically, this study sought to identify an optimal AP-1 inhibitory core and to systematically determine whether controlled modulation of NLS-associated linker rigidity could preserve targeted interface engagement while minimizing nonspecific electrostatic interference at the protein–DNA binding site.

Methods

Peptide dataset construction

Bioactive peptide sequences (<15 amino acids) were curated from peer-reviewed literature and standardized in one-letter amino acid notation (Table 1). A previously reported AP-1 inhibitory tripeptide (Kumar et al. 2021) was included as a benchmark. Its 3D structure was retrieved

Table 1. Bioactive peptides included in the computational screening dataset, showing sequence, length, reported activity, organism source, and reference. aa = amino acids; ACE = angiotensin-converting enzyme.

	Peptide sequence	Length (aa)	Reported activity	Organism	Reference
1	SKWQHQQDSC	10	Anticancer/colorectal cancer	<i>Glycine max</i> (soybean)	Fernández-Tomé et al. 2017
2	RKQLQGVN	8	anticancer	<i>Glycine max</i> (soybean)	
3	GFAGDDAPRA	10	Antioxidant	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> (watermelon)	Zhu et al. 2022
4	RVFDGAV	7	ACE inhibitor	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> seeds	Ma et al. 2019
5	TNLDWY	6	ACE inhibitor	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> Seeds	
6	QPYPQPQ	8	Antioxidant	wheat germ protein	Zhang et al. 2023
7	PVLGPVRGPFPLL	13	Anti-inflammatory	wheat germ protein	
8	ECFSTA	6	Anti-inflammatory	wheat germ protein	

from the ChEBI database (ID: 144557) and processed using the same modeling and docking workflow as the screened peptides.

Peptide structure modeling

Three-dimensional peptide structures were generated using PEP-FOLD3 (Thévenet et al. 2012). Multiple conformations were produced per sequence, ranked using the sOPEP energy score, and the top-ranked model was selected for docking. All structures were visually inspected to confirm reasonable backbone geometry and absence of steric clashes.

Target preparation and grid definition

The crystal structure of the AP-1 transcriptional complex (PDB ID: 1FOS) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (RCSB). Protein preparation was performed using the Schrödinger Protein Preparation Wizard. The workflow included assignment of bond orders, addition of hydrogen atoms, optimization of hydrogen bonding networks, determination of protonation states at physiological pH (7.4), and restrained energy minimization using the OPLS4 force field to relieve steric clashes while preserving crystallographic geometry.

Docking grids were generated using the Peptide Docking interface in the Schrödinger Suite. The grid was centered to encompass the biologically validated AP-1 protein–DNA interaction interface, based on previously reported interaction residues (Kumar et al. 2021). Specifically, residues and nucleotides retained within the grid definition included:

- Chain A: DG8, DA9;
- Chain B: DG30, DA31;
- Chain E: SER154;
- Chain F: ARG279.

These regions correspond to the bZIP domain and DNA-contact interface critical for AP-1 transcriptional activity. The grid box dimensions were adjusted to fully enclose this composite protein–DNA interaction region.

For each independent docking run, 10 poses were retained, and GlideScore (kcal/mol) was used as the primary scoring function for ranking predicted binding conformations.

Moreover, two trivial negative control peptides, poly-glycine and poly-aspartate sequences, were additionally docked under the same grid definition and scoring conditions used for the screened peptides.

Molecular dynamics simulation

The top-ranked peptide–AP-1 complex was subjected to all-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulation using the Desmond simulation package (Schrödinger LLC) (Bowers et al. 2006).

The prepared complex was embedded in an orthorhombic simulation box with a minimum buffer distance of 10 Å between the protein surface and box boundaries to prevent periodic self-interactions. The system was solvated using the TIP3P explicit water model. Appropriate counterions (Na⁺) were added to neutralize the system charge, and additional NaCl was introduced to achieve a physiological salt concentration of 0.15 M.

Energy minimization was first performed to remove unfavorable contacts, followed by a multi-stage equilibration protocol under default Desmond relaxation settings. Initial equilibration was conducted under the NVT ensemble at 300 K using the Nose–Hoover thermostat to stabilize temperature. This was followed by NPT equilibration at 1 atm using the Martyna–Tobias–Klein barostat to ensure pressure stabilization and proper system density.

Production dynamics were carried out for 200 ns under NPT conditions at 300 K and 1 atm. The OPLS4 force field was employed for all bonded and non-bonded interactions. A time step of 2 fs was used, and long-range electrostatics were treated using the particle mesh Ewald (PME) method. A cutoff radius of 9 Å was applied for short-range van der Waals and electrostatic interactions. Trajectory frames were recorded at 100 ps intervals for subsequent analysis.

Post-simulation analyses included root-mean-square deviation (RMSD), root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF), secondary structure evolution, and protein–ligand interaction profiling to evaluate structural convergence and interfacial stability throughout the trajectory (Dagliyan et al. 2011; Hospital et al. 2015; Hollingsworth and Dror 2018; Knapp et al. 2018).

Design of nuclear-targeted peptide variants

The lead peptide was extended with a classical nuclear localization signal (PKKKRKV) at the C-terminus. Four constructs were generated:

- (i) MP-1: direct NLS fusion;

- (ii) MP-2: flexible linker (GGGGS) + NLS;
- (iii) MP-3: rigid linker (EAAAK) + NLS;
- (iv) MP-4: double rigid linker ((EAAAK)₂) + NLS.

Structures were modeled using PEP-FOLD3 (Thévenet et al. 2012), and top-ranked conformations were selected for docking.

CABS-dock flexible docking

Peptide–linker–NLS constructs were docked using CABS-dock (Kurcinski et al. 2015), allowing fully flexible peptide docking without predefined binding-site constraints. Clustering analysis was performed, and docking outcomes were evaluated using dominant cluster density and RMSD values. Representative poses from the most populated clusters were selected for comparative analysis.

In silico antigenicity and immunogenicity assessment

To preliminarily evaluate potential immunogenic liability of the engineered peptide construct (SKWQH-QQDSCEAAAKEAAAKPKKKRKV), computational antigenicity screening was performed prior to future experimental evaluation.

Antigenicity prediction was conducted using the VaxiJen v2.0 server (Doytchinova and Flower 2007), an alignment-independent method based on auto cross covariance (ACC) transformation of amino acid physicochemical properties. The tumor model was selected, and the default threshold of 0.4 was applied as recommended by the developers.

To strengthen predictive confidence, additional analyses were performed using ANTIGENpro (Magnan et al. 2010), a pathogen-independent sequence-based machine learning predictor, and the IEDB Analysis Resource (Vita et al. 2019) for preliminary MHC class I and II binding epitope screening. All analyses were conducted using the full-length modified peptide sequence, and default parameters were maintained to avoid bias introduced by manual threshold adjustment.

Results and discussion

Peptide structural modeling and conformational diversity

Given the central regulatory role of AP-1 across inflammation, oxidative stress, proliferation, and oncogenic signaling (Angel and Karin 1991; Shaulian and Karin 2002; Eferl and Wagner 2003; Papavassiliou et al. 2023), a structurally diverse peptide library was curated to enable unbiased computational screening (Table 1). Rather than restricting candidates to previously annotated anticancer peptides, sequences associated with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antihypertensive, antimicrobial, and antiproliferative activities were included to minimize annotation

Table 2. Nuclear-targeted peptide variants generated from the lead AP-1-binding core, indicating linker type, NLS incorporation, final sequence, length, and design rationale. aa = amino acids; NLS = nuclear localization signal.

Core peptide sequence	Name	Linker type	NLS	Final peptide sequence	Length (aa)	Design intent and rationale
SKWQHQQDSC	Pep-1	no	no	SKWQHQQDSC	10	Minimal AP-1-binding motif identified during screening; serves as a baseline for target engagement without delivery enhancement.
SKWQHQQDSC	MP-1	no	PKKKRKV	SKWQHQQDSCPKKKRKV	17	Direct fusion of NLS to enable nuclear targeting; assesses whether nuclear localization can be achieved without structural separation from the binding epitope.
SKWQHQQDSC	MP-2	GGGGS	PKKKRKV	SKWQHQQDSCGGGSPKKKRKV	22	Introduces conformational flexibility to decouple the NLS from the binding region, allowing independent sampling but with increased structural freedom.
SKWQHQQDSC	MP-3	EAAAK	PKKKRKV	SKWQHQQDSC EAAAKPKKKRKV	22	Enforces partial spatial separation between binding and delivery domains while maintaining compactness.
SKWQHQQDSC	MP-4	EAAAKEAAK	PKKKRKV	SKWQHQQDSC EAAAKEAAKPKKKRKV	27	Maximizes structural segregation of AP-1 binding and nuclear-targeting functions, minimizing NLS interference while preserving core peptide engagement.

bias and reflect the pleiotropic nature of AP-1 signaling (Fernández-Tomé et al. 2017; Zhu et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2023).

Three-dimensional structures were generated using PEP-FOLD3 (Thévenet et al. 2012), and dominant conformations are summarized in Table 3. Clear length-dependent conformational differences were observed. Short peptides (6–8 residues) predominantly adopted flexible coil structures, consistent with limited intrinsic secondary stabilization at this scale and the known structural plasticity of short linear peptides (Fosgerau and Hoffmann 2015). In contrast, intermediate-length peptides (9–13 residues) exhibited partial structural organization, including turn-rich motifs and short helical segments.

Notably, the soybean-derived peptide SKWQHQQDSC (Pep-1) adopted a compact and partially ordered conformation. Such pre-organization is advantageous when targeting extended protein–protein or protein–DNA interfaces, where balanced conformational adaptability and structural definition enhance productive binding (Chen et al. 2013; London et al. 2013). All models were free of steric clashes or non-physical geometries, supporting their suitability for docking analyses.

Docking protocol validation

Peptide–protein docking was performed using the Glide module (Schrödinger LLC) in Standard Precision (SP) mode. Although Glide was originally developed for small-molecule docking (Friesner et al. 2004), its SP-Pep-tide protocol incorporates enhanced conformational sampling and has demonstrated reliable performance in modeling flexible peptide–protein interactions in benchmarking studies (Tubert-Brohman et al. 2013). Furthermore, the Schrödinger suite has been successfully applied to protein–peptide docking investigations in multiple structural studies (Bhachoo and Beuming 2017).

To further contextualize the docking workflow, trivial negative control peptides were also evaluated under identical conditions. The poly-glycine control returned a weak GlideScore (−2.864 kcal/mol), whereas the poly-aspartate control did not yield a meaningful docking result within the applied protocol. These observations support the discriminative behavior of the docking setup and indicate that the stronger ranking of the lead peptide was not reproduced by trivial sequence controls.

Peptides were treated as fully flexible ligands during docking. It is important to note that docking scores do not represent the absolute free energy of binding (ΔG) and cannot by themselves confirm true peptide binding. Rather, docking provides an approximate estimate of the favorability of the complex within the assumptions of the scoring function and is most appropriately used for relative ranking of candidate poses or ligands. Accordingly, the docking results in the present study should be interpreted as comparative *in silico* evidence of interaction favorability rather than definitive proof of binding affinity. Binding poses were ranked using GlideScore (kcal/mol), and the top-scoring pose for each peptide was selected for detailed interaction analysis. The reference AP-1 inhibitory tripeptide (Kumar et al. 2021) was docked under identical grid and scoring conditions to ensure methodological consistency and allow direct comparative evaluation.

Docking calculations were conducted against the AP-1 transcriptional complex (PDB ID: 1FOS), focusing on chains A, B, E, and F encompassing the bZIP dimerization domain and DNA-binding interface. The docking grid was positioned according to structurally and functionally validated AP-1 regulatory regions (Ozanne et al. 2007; Papavassiliou et al. 2023), ensuring biologically relevant sampling of the interaction hotspot.

Redocking of the literature reference tripeptide (EER) reproduced its previously reported binding orientation and interaction pattern (Kumar et al. 2021), thereby con-

Table 3. Representative PEP-FOLD3-predicted three-dimensional conformations of selected peptides, indicating dominant secondary structure tendencies and structural compactness.

N	Sequence	3D structure	Predicted dominant conformation	Structural description
1	SKWQHQQDSC		Partial helix / turn-rich	Compact fold with short ordered segments
2	RKQLQGVN		Random coil	Short, flexible peptide with minimal secondary structure
3	GFAGDDAPRA		Turn-rich	Compact with local bends
4	RVFDGAV		Random coil	Very short, structurally flexible
5	TNLDWY		Random coil	Minimal structural constraint
6	QPYPQPQ		Coil	Proline-rich flexible structure
7	PVLGPVRGPFPLL		Partial helix	Moderately structured with transient helicity
8	ECFSTA		Random coil	Short, flexible peptide

firming the reliability and internal consistency of the docking protocol. Standardized docking parameters were maintained throughout all calculations to ensure that observed affinity differences reflected intrinsic peptide structural properties rather than methodological variability.

Comparative docking and identification of the lead peptide

Glide docking revealed clear affinity differences among screened peptides (Table 4). Several candidates outperformed the reference tripeptide (−5.964 kcal/mol), indicating comparatively more favorable predicted docking under the applied conditions.

Table 4. Docking binding scores (kcal/mol) of selected peptides against the AP-1 transcription factor (PDB ID: 1FOS; chains A, B, E, and F) calculated using Glide in Maestro (Schrödinger LLC). Docking was conducted in Standard Precision (SP) mode, and the best-scoring pose per peptide is reported. Lower GlideScore values correspond to higher predicted binding affinity.

Number	Peptide number	Docking score Kcal/mol
1	Pep-1	−9.396
2	Pep-3	−9.034
3	Pep-5	−8.975
4	Pep-6	−7.809
5	Pep-7	−6.597
6	Pep-8	−7.767
7	Pep-9	−7.779
8	Pep-10	−7.243
9	Reference peptide	−5.964
10	Negative control (DDDDDDDDDD)	No meaningful docking result
11	Negative control (GGGGGGGGGG)	−2.864

Pep-1 (SKWQHQQDSC) showed the most favorable GlideScore (−9.396 kcal/mol), followed by Pep-3 and Pep-5 (Table 4). Shorter, minimally structured peptides generally displayed weaker affinities, suggesting that partial conformational pre-organization enhances engagement of the extended AP-1 interface. This observation aligns with established relationships between interfacial complementarity and binding affinity in protein–peptide recognition (Dagliyan et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2013).

Interaction mapping of Pep-1 (Fig. 1; Table 5) revealed a dual engagement mode involving both AP-1 protein residues and DNA bases. Hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions were observed with DNA bases in chains A/B, alongside stabilizing contacts with residues in chains E and F, including ARG E:158, LYS F:277, ARG F:272, LYS F:280, and GLU F:290. Hydrogen bonding and salt-bridge formation with DNA were observed in both chains A and B. Such a composite interaction topology suggests potential interference at the protein–DNA recognition interface, a strategy increasingly explored for transcription factor targeting (Lambert et al. 2018; Yin 2019).

In contrast, the reference tripeptide EER (Fig. 2; Table 5) demonstrated binding within the major groove region of the AP-1 complex, engaging DNA bases in chain B as well as protein residues within chains E and F. Consistent with the literature (Kumar et al. 2021), hydrogen bonding with DG B:30 and DA B:31 and interaction with SER E:154 were observed. Although minor residue-level differences were noted relative to the original report – likely reflecting differences in docking protocol and scoring – the overall binding topology remained confined to the canonical AP-1 protein–DNA interface. Compared with Pep-1, the interaction network

Figure 1. Structural and interaction analysis of the top-ranked AP-1 inhibitory peptide docked to the AP-1 complex. Protein–ligand interaction diagram of the lead peptide Pep-1 (SKWQHQQDSC) docked against the AP-1 transcription factor complex (PDB ID: 1FOS; chains A, B, E, and F). Hydrogen bonds, electrostatic interactions, hydrophobic contacts, and DNA interactions are shown. The diagram illustrates dual engagement of AP-1 protein residues and DNA bases within the composite protein–DNA interface.

Figure 2. Structural and interaction analysis of the reference AP-1 inhibitory peptide docked to the AP-1 complex (chains A, B, E, and F). The upper panel illustrates the three-dimensional binding orientation of the peptide relative to the AP-1 dimer–DNA assembly. The lower panel presents the corresponding two-dimensional protein–ligand interaction diagram. Interactions include hydrogen bonds (purple arrows), salt bridges (blue lines), π -cation contacts (red lines), hydrophobic interactions (green-highlighted residues), and polar contacts (cyan residues), as defined in the interaction legend. Charged residues are indicated in orange (negative) and blue (positive), whereas solvent-exposed regions and hydration sites are shown in gray. The peptide engages primarily with residues in chains E and F, with localized DNA-base contacts, supporting binding within the AP-1 protein–DNA interface.

Table 5. Detailed interaction profile of the reference tripeptide (EER) and Pep-1 docked to the AP-1 transcriptional complex (PDB ID: 1FOS), highlighting residue-specific contacts across protein chains and DNA bases.

Feature	Reference peptide (EER)	Pep-1 (SKWQHQQDSC)
Docking score (kcal/mol)	−5.964	−9.396
Protein chains involved	Chains E and F	E, F
Direct protein hydrogen bonds	LYS F:280;	ARG E:158
	ARG E:158;	ARG E:157
	SER E:154;	ARG F:272
	SER F:276	LYS F:277
		LYS F:280
		GLU F:290
Electrostatic contacts (proximity)	LYS F:280;	LYS F:288
	LYS F:282	LYS F:280
Hydrophobic contacts	ALA E:151;	ILE F:286
	LEU F:283	ALA F:287
Direct DNA hydrogen bonds	DG B:30;	DG A:17
	DA B:31	DA B:28
		DT B:29
		DA B:31
		DC B:32
Binding interface topology	Predominantly protein–surface engagement with localized DNA base interactions (chain B)	Composite protein–DNA interface engagement (major-groove associated), with multi-point anchoring to DNA bases (chains A/B) and stabilizing contacts with AP-1 residues (chains E/F).

of the reference peptide appears more localized and less extensively distributed across the composite interface, which may contribute to its comparatively weaker predicted binding affinity. Collectively, these results identify SKWQHQQDSC as the most promising AP-1-binding core for subsequent engineering. Although the reference peptide provided a useful comparative benchmark under identical docking conditions, it is acknowledged that the present validation remains limited to a small set of trivial negative controls rather than an experimentally established peptide benchmark panel. In this context, the docking workflow should still be considered hypothesis-generating and prioritization-oriented rather than fully validated for definitive binder/non-binder classification. Future studies may further strengthen this framework by incorporating experimentally characterized positive peptide binders, where available, together with broader negative control sets such as composition-matched sequence reshuffles. Because interaction-site prediction for protein complexes remains challenging and method-dependent, docking outcomes should be interpreted as prioritization evidence rather than definitive proof of binding (Zhou and Qin 2007).

Linker engineering and NLS integration: CABS-dock evaluation

To enable nuclear targeting while preserving inhibitory specificity, Pep-1 was extended with a classical nuclear

Table 6. Model-based structural characterization of engineered AP-1–targeted peptide variants. PEP-FOLD3 predictions reveal length- and linker-dependent modulation of secondary structure, compactness, and domain separation between the inhibitory motif and appended NLS sequence.

Final peptide sequence	Pepfold 3 structure	Linker type	Structural description (dominant features)	Predicted dominant conformation (from model)
SKWQHQQDSC		None	Compact short peptide showing a brief α -helical tendency with terminal flexibility; minimal length limits long-range stabilization but retains a defined local fold.	Original peptide; short helical segment/helix–turn motif
SKWQHQQDSCPKKKRKV		None	Core region retains partial secondary structure, while the appended cationic NLS behaves more flexibly/extended, giving an overall compact–semi-flexible architecture.	Mixed helix + disordered tail
SKWQHQQDSCGGGGSPKKKRKV		GGGGS (flexible)	Flexible spacer introduces a hinge-like region, increasing conformational freedom; the structure appears more extended and dynamic, with secondary structure distributed into separate short elements rather than one continuous helix.	Predominantly flexible/coil with transient helices
SKWQHQQDSC EAAAKPKKKRKV		EAAAK (rigid α -helical)	The EAAAK segment promotes a stable helix that organizes the construct into a more directional, rod-like shape, reducing folding back of the NLS onto the core.	Predominantly α -helical
SKWQHQQDSC EAAAKEAAAKPKKKRKV		(EAAAK) ₂ (double rigid)	Displays the most pronounced continuous α -helix and highest structural segregation between the core peptide and NLS; geometry is elongated and rigid, consistent with a “spacer” role that minimizes domain interference.	Strongly α -helical (extended helix)

localization signal (PKKKRKV) (Lange et al. 2007) using linker architectures of increasing rigidity (Table 6). Nuclear transport relies on importin-mediated recognition of positively charged NLS motifs (Görlich and Kutay 1999), but excessive charge density may promote nonspecific electrostatic interactions if not structurally controlled.

Flexible blind docking using CABS-dock (Kurcinski et al. 2015; Kmiecik et al. 2016) enabled comparative evaluation of structural convergence and domain segregation (Table 7).

Direct NLS fusion (MP-1) improved docking convergence but introduced extensive electrostatic involvement of the NLS in AP-1 binding, suggesting charge-driven interaction inflation. Insertion of a flexible GGGGS linker (MP-2), a commonly used flexible spacer (van Rosmalen et al. 2017), increased conformational freedom but resulted in a more diffuse interaction footprint.

Rigid linker strategies produced clearer structural control. The single EAAAK construct (MP-3) demonstrated improved cluster density and reduced peripheral NLS

involvement. The EAAAK motif is known to promote α -helical rigidity and domain separation (Arai et al. 2001; Chen et al. 2013). The structural role of linkers in controlling domain spacing and conformational behavior has also been demonstrated in chimeric protein systems, where linker variation influences global architecture and functional separation (Arai et al. 2004).

Most notably, the double rigid linker construct (MP-4) exhibited the lowest average RMSD and strongest clustering convergence (Table 7), with minimal NLS participation in the binding hotspot. These findings align with established principles of fusion-protein linker engineering, where α -helical spacers enforce spatial segregation between functional domains (George and Heringa 2002; Chen et al. 2013).

These results establish a clear structure–function trajectory: progressive rigidification enforces spatial segregation between inhibitory and targeting domains, preserving mechanistic clarity while maintaining binding convergence.

Table 7. Structure–function evaluation of engineered AP-1–targeted peptides based on CABS-dock clustering metrics. Progressive linker rigidification modulates docking convergence, RMSD dispersion, and NLS involvement, supporting controlled spatial segregation between the inhibitory core and nuclear localization domain.

Peptide system	Construct features	Length (aa)	Dominant cluster density	Avg RMSD (Å)	Max RMSD (Å)	Models in dominant cluster	Core peptide involvement	Binding focus
Original peptide	No NLS, no linker	10	20.70	7.92	19.92	164	Moderate, conserved	AP-1 protein surface
MP-1 (NLS only)	Direct NLS fusion	17	27.48	5.82	23.84	160	Preserved	Broadened surface
MP-2 (Flexible linker)	GGGGS linker + NLS	22	26.26	5.22	20.32	137	Preserved	Diffuse interface
MP-3 (Single rigid linker)	EAAAK + NLS	22	31.39	5.89	15.73	185	Strong, conserved	Focused interface
MP-4 (Double rigid linker)	EAAAK×2 + NLS	27	26.36	4.36	20.43	115	Strong, highly conserved	Highly focused

Molecular dynamics simulation of the native 10-residue complex

To evaluate the dynamic stability of the lead peptide (Pep-1) within the AP-1 interface, a 200 ns all-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was performed using the Desmond engine (Bowers et al. 2006) under explicit solvent conditions with OPLS4 force field parameters.

For MD refinement, the DNA component of the crystallographic AP-1 structure was removed to specifically assess peptide–protein interfacial stability independent of large-scale nucleic acid fluctuations. Such system reduction is commonly employed in focused protein–peptide MD studies when the primary objective is evaluation of interfacial persistence rather than full protein–DNA dynamics (Hospital et al. 2015; Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

Following equilibration, backbone RMSD of the AP-1 bZIP domain stabilized within approximately 2–3.5 Å without progressive drift throughout the production

phase (Fig. 3), indicating structural convergence and maintenance of the native fold. Avoidance of artificial stability through replica bias is critical in MD interpretation (Knapp et al. 2018).

Secondary structure analysis confirmed preservation of the α -helical architecture characteristic of the AP-1 basic leucine zipper domain. Maintenance of helical content throughout the trajectory indicates that peptide binding does not destabilize the transcription factor scaffold.

Peptide RMSD exhibited initial equilibration followed by plateau stabilization, consistent with conformational adaptation rather than dissociation (Dagliyan et al. 2011). Residue-level interaction analysis revealed persistent hydrogen bonds and electrostatic contacts, particularly involving ARG E:157 and ARG E:158 (Fig. 6), supporting stable interfacial anchoring.

Collectively, these results support the dynamic persistence of the native inhibitory core within the AP-1 protein interface over the simulated timescale under the modeled conditions.

Protein-Ligand RMSD

Figure 3. Root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) analysis of the native 10-residue peptide–AP-1 complex during a 200 ns molecular dynamics simulation. The protein backbone RMSD (C α) demonstrates equilibration and stabilization after ~20–30 ns, whereas ligand RMSD (fit on protein) shows initial conformational adaptation followed by plateau stabilization, indicating persistent binding without dissociation.

Root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) analysis further resolved residue-level flexibility patterns within the peptide-AP-1 complex (Figs 4, 5). The AP-1 bZIP domain exhibited predominantly low-to-moderate fluctuations ($\sim 2\text{--}3\text{ \AA}$), with higher mobility confined to peripheral loop regions rather than the core helical interface.

Importantly, residues directly participating in peptide binding displayed comparatively restrained fluctuations, consistent with interface rigidification upon complex formation, a characteristic feature of stable protein-peptide recognition (Dagliyan et al. 2011; Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

Figure 4. Root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) profile of AP-1 C α atoms during a 200 ns simulation of the native peptide complex. Most residues exhibit moderate fluctuations ($\sim 2\text{--}3\text{ \AA}$), with localized flexibility peaks corresponding to loop or interfacial regions, while the structured bZIP domain remains stable.

Figure 5. Ligand RMSF profile of the native 10-residue peptide during a 200 ns molecular dynamics simulation. Elevated fluctuations are observed primarily at terminal residues, reflecting intrinsic peptide flexibility, whereas core interface residues display comparatively restrained motion, supporting stable anchoring within the AP-1 binding interface.

Ligand-Protein Contacts

Figure 6. Ligand–protein interaction network obtained from molecular dynamics simulation of the native 10-residue peptide in complex with the AP-1 transcription factor (PDB ID: 1FOS). The diagram summarizes persistent interactions observed during the trajectory, including hydrogen bonds, electrostatic contacts, π -cation interactions, hydrophobic contacts, and water-mediated bridges. Positively charged residues (blue), negatively charged residues (orange), and hydrophobic residues (green) are indicated according to interaction type. The interaction network highlights dominant electrostatic anchoring and water-bridged stabilization at the AP-1 binding interface.

For the peptide, elevated RMSF values were primarily observed at terminal residues, reflecting the intrinsic flexibility of short linear peptides in aqueous environments. In contrast, central residues contributing to the binding interface exhibited reduced fluctuation amplitudes, supporting stable anchoring within the AP-1 interaction surface. This differential mobility pattern suggests that binding is mediated by a structurally adaptive yet interface-focused mechanism, in which terminal flexibility coexists with conserved interfacial stabilization. Collectively, the RMSF data reinforce the structural convergence indicated by RMSD analysis and provide residue-level evidence of persistent complex stabilization. Nevertheless, these MD findings should be interpreted with appropriate caution. A 200 ns MD simulation remains limited relative to the much longer timescales on which association and dissociation events may occur in real systems, and the absence of dissociation within this time window does not by itself establish strong binding *in vitro* or *in vivo*. In addition, all-atom MD simulations depend on force-field approximations that may over-stabilize certain interactions. Therefore, the present simulations are best interpreted as supportive evidence of structural persistence within the

simulated window rather than definitive proof of long-term binding stability or biological activity.

Design implications

The integrated docking and molecular dynamics analyses define linker rigidity as a decisive determinant of structural fidelity in chimeric peptide engineering. Direct NLS fusion enhances electrostatic convergence but risks nonspecific surface engagement driven by charge density. Excessive flexibility introduces interaction ambiguity and reduces geometric focusing.

In contrast, α -helical linker duplication promotes spatial segregation between inhibitory and targeting domains, preserving mechanistic specificity while maintaining docking convergence. This principle is consistent with established strategies in modular peptide and fusion protein design (Arai et al. 2001; Chen et al. 2013).

Together, this rational computational framework establishes a reproducible strategy for engineering nuclear-targeted peptide inhibitors of transcription factors traditionally regarded as challenging therapeutic targets (Darnell 2002; Lambert et al. 2018).

Table 8. Pairs of peptide/receptor residues closer than 4.5 Å in the selected complex (double rigid linker).

Receptor residue	Peptide residue	Receptor residue	Peptide residue	Receptor residue	Peptide residue
LEU F 317	PRO A 21	LEU F 317	LYS A 24	LYS F 320	LYS A 24
LEU F 310	ALA A 14	LEU F 310	ALA A 18	GLN F 316	LYS A 26
THR F 306	LYS A 15	MET F 309	ALA A 18	MET F 309	LYS A 22
GLU F 302	GLU A 11	LEU F 303	GLU A 11	THR F 306	ALA A 14
GLN F 299	GLN A 4	GLN F 299	ASP A 8	GLN F 299	GLU A 11
GLU E 194	PRO A 21	LYS F 292	SER A 1	LEU F 296	SER A 1
LEU E 187	ALA A 17	LYS E 190	ALA A 17	LYS E 190	PRO A 21
GLN E 180	GLN A 7	GLN E 180	CYS A 10	ILE E 183	ALA A 14
GLU E 173	SER A 1	LYS E 176	GLN A 7	SER E 177	GLN A 7

Antigenicity prediction and immunogenic risk evaluation

To preliminarily assess potential immunogenic liability of the engineered peptide construct (SKWQHQQD-SCEAAAKEAAKPKKKRKV), multiple complementary *in silico* prediction platforms were employed (Table 9).

VaxiJen v2.0 analysis yielded a score of 0.579 under the tumor model (threshold 0.4), classifying the sequence as a probable antigen at the level of global physicochemical properties. It is important to note that VaxiJen employs an alignment-independent auto cross covariance (ACC) transformation of amino acid descriptors and does not explicitly model antigen processing, MHC binding, or T-cell receptor recognition (Doytchinova and Flower 2007). Consequently, VaxiJen predictions reflect overall antigen-like sequence features rather than direct immunogenic epitope formation.

In contrast, ANTIGENpro predicted a very low antigenicity probability (0.010). Unlike descriptor-based approaches, ANTIGENpro utilizes machine learning models trained on protein microarray immunoreactivity data, incorporating broader sequence-derived features (Magnan et al. 2010). The marked reduction in predicted antigenicity probability suggests limited intrinsic immunoreactivity potential.

To further refine risk estimation, MHC class I and class II binding analyses were performed using the IEDB Analysis Resource, which integrates experimentally validated epitope datasets and consensus prediction algorithms (Vita et al. 2019). No strong high-affinity binders were identified across the full HLA reference panel under default percentile rank thresholds. Importantly, no dominant CD8⁺ or CD4⁺ T-cell epitope hotspots were predicted within the therapeutic core region (SKWQHQQDSC). Weak predicted binders were primarily localized to the appended polybasic NLS segment, consistent with the

known influence of lysine- and arginine-rich regions on computational epitope scoring.

The apparent discrepancy between VaxiJen and MHC-based predictions likely reflects the high density of charged residues introduced by the nuclear localization signal rather than the presence of structured immunodominant epitopes. Importantly, computational antigenicity classification does not directly equate to clinical immunogenicity, which is governed by antigen processing, presentation, tolerance mechanisms, and exposure context (De Groot and Scott 2007; Baker and Reynolds 2010).

Given the absence of strong predicted MHC binders and the exclusively *in silico* scope of the present study, the overall immunogenic risk of the construct is considered low at this stage of development. Nevertheless, experimental validation would be required prior to systemic or *in vivo* therapeutic application.

Conclusion

This study presents a rational *in silico* framework for the design of nuclear-targeted peptide inhibitors against the AP-1 transcriptional complex. Through systematic structure-guided screening, the soybean-derived decapeptide SKWQHQQDSC emerged as the top-ranked candidate within the curated peptide library, demonstrating dual engagement of the protein–DNA interface and superior docking performance relative to the benchmark peptide under the applied scoring conditions.

Molecular dynamics simulations further supported the persistence of the native 10-residue peptide at the AP-1 interface while preserving the structural integrity of the AP-1 bZIP α -helical domain over the simulated timescale. However, these findings should be interpreted as supportive computational evidence rather than definitive proof of long-term binding stability or biological activity.

Table 9. *In silico* antigenicity and immunogenicity assessment of the engineered peptide construct (SKWQHQQDSC-EAAAKEAAK-PKPKKKRKV).

Analysis tool	Model/parameters	Output	Interpretation
VaxiJen v2.0	Tumor model, threshold 0.4	Score = 0.579	Classified as a probable antigen at the sequence-property level
ANTIGENpro	Default parameters	Probability = 0.010	Very low predicted antigenicity probability
IEDB MHC-I	Full HLA reference set	No strong binders (<1–2% rank)	No dominant CD8 T-cell epitope hotspots predicted
IEDB MHC-II	Full HLA reference set	No strong binders (<2% rank)	No dominant CD4 T-cell epitope hotspots predicted

Progressive incorporation of a classical nuclear localization signal (NLS) revealed that linker architecture is a decisive determinant of structural fidelity. Flexible or directly fused NLS constructs increased electrostatic participation and reduced interaction discipline, whereas α -helical EAAAK linkers, particularly in duplicated form, enforced spatial segregation between inhibitory and targeting domains. The double rigid-linker construct demonstrated the highest structural convergence and the most focused AP-1 engagement in flexible docking analyses.

Collectively, this work defines linker rigidity as a critical design parameter in multifunctional peptide engineering and establishes a reproducible computational workflow for developing nuclear-directed peptide candidates against transcription factors traditionally considered challenging drug targets. The optimized construct therefore represents a structurally justified candidate for future experimental validation.

*Detailed residue-residue contact maps were generated for all linker variants; however, only the optimized double rigid linker construct is shown in the main manuscript to highlight the final, functionally relevant interaction mode, whereas the remaining maps are provided as Suppl. material 1.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

AI-assisted language support was used during manuscript preparation to improve clarity, grammar, and academic phrasing. The authors reviewed, verified, and approved all AI-assisted edits and remain fully responsible for the scientific content, analysis, interpretation, and conclusions.

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Author contributions

Z.A. conceived and designed the study, performed the computational experiments, analyzed the data, and drafted the manuscript. I.A. contributed to study conceptualization, provided scientific supervision, and critically revised the manuscript. A.A. contributed to methodological guidance, data interpretation, and manuscript review. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Zahraa Amer Al-Juboori <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2115-2965>

Inam Sameh Arif <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9194-1919>

Ayman Albanna <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8514-2774>

Data availability

The crystal structure of AP-1 (PDB ID: 1FOS) was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org>). All computational models and simulation trajectories are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

The datasets generated or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. Representative structures and quantitative docking results are included in this published article.

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Supplementary material 1

Additional docking and molecular dynamics analyses

Authors: Zahraa Amer Al-Juboori, Inam Sameh Arif, Ayman Albanna

Data type: pdf

Explanation note: This supplementary file contains the full molecular dynamics simulation report generated from the 200 ns Desmond simulation of the peptide–AP-1 complex. The report includes RMSD, RMSE, secondary structure analysis, interaction profiling, and trajectory-based stability assessment supporting the structural conclusions presented in the main manuscript.

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